

**ESTIMATING
POST-CONSUMER
FIBREBOARD WASTE
GENERATION IN
EUROPE**

**PROJECT INNOVATION
FACTSHEET**

Medium-density fibreboard (MDF) use has grown steadily since the 1990s and increasing volumes are now reaching end-of-life. EcoReFibre provides an interactive tool that estimates MDF volumes over time. It aims to support planning for sorting and fibre recovery capacity, as well as investment and policy decisions.

MODEL OVERVIEW

Interactive charts show:

- Apparent MDF consumption.
- Projected MDF waste volumes.

Coverage:

- World, EU27, France, Germany and Sweden.

Method and data:

- Apparent consumption is calculated as production plus imports minus exports.
- End use shares are informed by European Panel Federation data.
- Product lifespans are based on large-scale surveys of end users.

Scenario settings:

- Geography and forecast type.
- Import adjustments from 0% to 200%.
- Average product lifespan from 6 to 15 years, default 12.

WHO IS IT FOR?

- Recyclers and waste operators to plan sorting capacity and future feedstock availability.
- Technology providers and investors to assess market potential and support investment decisions.
- Public authorities and policy makers to inform evidence-based planning for circular economy and waste management measures.

ecorefibre.eu/model/

PARTNERS

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